

ARMS

Supercapacitors:
Energize your world

Atomic Layer-coated Graphene Electrode-based Micro-flexible and Structural Supercapacitors

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Publishable Executive Summary

Deliverable D1.3 reports the baseline structure and electrochemical performance of carbon-based electrode materials developed in the ARMS project. The work evaluates bio-curved graphene carbons, and wood-derived carbons from different species, including black liquor and hybrid composites, and doped or post-processed variants.

The results show that alder-derived carbons (AWC) outperform other wood species, with AWC-3-700 achieving a surface area of $2844 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and capacitance of 265 F g^{-1} . Bio-curved carbons also delivered high capacitance ($>200 \text{ F g}^{-1}$), while black liquor alone performed poorly. However, AWC–ABL (activated black liquor) composites reached capacitance values up to 250 F g^{-1} , demonstrating some synergy between precursors. Doping and post-processing improved coulombic efficiency but generally reduced capacitance.

Overall, the study identifies AWC composites as the most promising candidates for flexible and structural supercapacitors. These results validate Milestone MS2 and enable the transition to upscaling, with 600 g of AWC-3-700 already produced and partly delivered for roll-to-roll electrode development.

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List of abbreviations

ABL – Activated Black Liquor
AWC – Alder Wood Carbon
BLC – Black Liquor Carbon
BWC – Birch Wood Carbon
CC – Constant Current
CE – Coulombic Efficiency
CMC – Carboxymethyl Cellulose
 C_{sp} – specific capacitance
CV – Cyclic Voltammetry
DCDA – Dicyandiamide
DMF – Dimethylformamide
EWC – Eucalyptus Wood Carbon
GCD – Galvanostatic Charge–Discharge
LC – Leakage Current
N-doped – nitrogen-doped
OWC – Oak Wood Carbon
P-doped – phosphorus-doped
rGO – Reduced Graphene Oxide
SBR – Styrene–Butadiene Rubber
 S_{BET} – Specific Surface Area (Brunauer–Emmett–Teller method)
SC – Supercapacitor
SEM – Scanning Electron Microscopy
XPS – X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy
XRD – X-ray Diffraction

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Description of deliverable

1. Introduction

The deliverable D1.3 describes the structure and electrochemical performance of the carbon materials synthesized in the ARMS project. It builds upon Deliverables D1.1 and D1.2, where the synthesis routes and initial materials development were reported, and to which the reader is referred for detailed information on the preparation processes.

The materials considered here were synthesized under WP1, specifically in Tasks T1.1 and T1.2, and subsequently characterized in T1.3. The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a consolidated overview of their baseline structural properties and electrochemical performance of the materials synthesized thus far, serving as a foundation for further development and, importantly, upscaling of the carbon-based materials.

This progress reported here also represents an important milestone (part of MS2 “Optimal electrode material and fabrication methods for flexible SCs and structural SCs composites” also due in M24, verified through D1.3), as it marks the transition of WP1 from laboratory-scale material synthesis and evaluation to the upscaling of the most promising candidates. The results summarized here are critical for guiding subsequent activities in other WPs, where the selected materials will undergo optimization, electrode integration, and supercapacitor device manufacturing. Deliverable D1.4, to be submitted in Month 36, will report on the outcomes of this next stage of materials upscaling in the 2-5 kg range.

2. Approach

2.1. Synthesis of the materials

Bio-curved graphene materials. For expanded description of the materials synthesis, please refer to deliverable D1.1. In brief, bio-curved graphene nanocarbons were synthesized from high-lignin biomass precursors, with pistachio nut shells identified as the optimal feedstock. The shells were first sorted to remove soft fractions, leaving only the hard lignocellulosic components. Pyrolysis was performed in a batch reactor under nitrogen flow (1430 mL min^{-1}), with a heating ramp of $280 \text{ }^\circ\text{C h}^{-1}$ up to $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, held for 2 h. The resulting bio-char was milled to a granulate size of $\sim 2 \text{ mm}$ and subsequently treated in 25 wt.% CaCl_2 solution for $>12 \text{ h}$ to remove impurities. After extensive washing in hot and demineralized water and drying at $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the material was obtained as the baseline bio-char precursor.

Activation was carried out by mixing the bio-char with KOH pellets (75 g char, 240 g KOH) in a stainless-steel vessel and heating under nitrogen flow with a ramp of $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C h}^{-1}$ up to $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. After passive cooling, the product was subjected to sequential washing: repeated hot water rinses, immersion in $>10\%$ HCl for $>12 \text{ h}$, and final demineralized water washes. The washed material was dried at $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for several hours and ground to a fine powder using a ball mill. The established synthesis yielded activated bio-curved graphene with surface areas exceeding $2000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and consistently delivering baseline electrochemical capacitance above 200 F g^{-1} .

Wood-derived carbon nanomaterials synthesis. For expanded description of the materials synthesis, please refer to deliverable D1.2. In brief, activated carbons were synthesized from various wood charcoals and other wood-based materials using a combined carbonization and chemical activation approach. The precursor was first carbonized at $400\text{--}500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, followed by mechanical grinding to achieve uniform particle size distribution ($\sim 5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$). For activation, the ground charcoal was impregnated with NaOH at mass ratios of 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 (precursor:activator) in the presence of deionized water. The activation was carried out under argon flow (100 L h^{-1}) at temperatures of 600, 700, 800, and $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h, using a sealed stainless-steel reactor. After cooling, the materials were thoroughly washed through sequential treatments with deionized water and concentrated HCl until neutral pH, followed by drying at $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The resulting activated carbons are referred to as MAT-X-YYY, where MAT denotes the type of starting material, X denotes the NaOH ratio and YYY the activation temperature. For a more thorough description of the synthesis the reader is referred to D1.2 “Baseline wood-derived graphene-containing nanomaterials synthesis parameters” submitted in M12 of the project.

The types of synthesized materials and the corresponding pre-fixes in the sample numbering are:

- Alder (AWC)
- Birch (BWC)
- Oak (OWC)
- Eucalyptus (EWC)
- Black liquor (BLC)

Furthermore, nitrogen-doped (N-doped) and phosphorus-doped (P-doped) variations of some of the materials have been synthesized, denoted by the suffix -N or -P at the end of the sample naming.

- For the nitrogen doping activated alder wood carbons were impregnated with dicyandiamide (DCDA) in ratio 1:20 in dimethylformamide (DMF), then the solvent was evaporated in rotary

evaporator, and the resulting solid mixture was treated at 800 °C in muffle oven on stream of argon (100 L h⁻¹) for one hour and then cooled.

- For phosphorous doping alder wood chips (4 mm fraction) were mixed with 85% phosphoric acid and deionized water to provide 1:2 and 1:3 precursor to acid ratios. Then the water was evaporated using heated stirrer, and the resulting mixtures were activated at 600 and 700 °C in muffle oven on stream of argon (100 L h⁻¹) for two hours. After cooling, the materials were thoroughly washed through sequential treatments with deionized water until neutral pH, dried at 105 °C, and then grinded using planetary mill for one hour.

Some of the materials undergo additional treatment for increased hydrophilicity / hydrophobicity, described in more detail in the sections corresponding to these materials.

- For the hydrophilicity increase alder wood activated carbon was mixed with 30% H₂O₂, oxidized at 60 °C using heated stirrer, and then dried at 105 °C (sample AWC-3-700+60min)
- For the hydrophilicity decrease alder wood activated carbon was tempered at 1000 °C in muffle oven on stream of argon (100 L h⁻¹) for one hour (sample AWC-3-700_T1000).

Black liquor materials were prepared using industrial black lignin from Kerha company. Hybrid black liquor and alder wood carbonizates were prepared using the above mentioned precursors. In the case of black liquor NaOH addition is always calculated on the dry mass of the precursor, which was determined using moisture analyzer. The water addition is not required and the rest of the procedure is the same as mentioned above for the charcoal. The samples based on black liquor are denoted as ABL and use the same convention for activation conditions as mentioned above, while hybrid samples are denoted as AWC-ABL-X/Y, where the X and Y, respectively, denote ratio of wood carbonizate and black liquor and the rest also follows the convention.

For sample naming convention provides detailed information about synthesis parameters:

- The number following the precursor code (e.g., 2 or 3 in AWC-2-700) denotes the activator amount used during chemical activation.
- The final digits (700 or 800) indicate the activation temperature in °C.
- AWC, BWC, OWC EWC and BLC denote alder, birch, oak, and eucalyptus wood, and black liquor carbons
- For composite samples (AWC-ABL), additional ratios such as 1/1 or 1/2 specify the mass ratio of AWC to ABL precursors used prior to activation.

2.2. Structural characterization

Nitrogen sorptometry analyses at 77K were conducted using a Quantachrome NOVA 4200K instrument to obtain comprehensive volumetric and surface area data, including surface area metrics, pore volume, and pore size distribution.

Elemental (ultimate) analysis was performed using Vario Macro device, oxygen content was calculated using mass difference.

The obtained materials have been characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using Rigaku MiniFlex600 X-ray diffractometer with Cu K α radiation. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the obtained

powders were taken by Thermo Scientific Helios 5 UX scanning electron microscope. Raman spectroscopy was performed using a TriVista CRS Confocal TR777.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was carried out for selected carbon materials using ThermoFisher ESCALAB Xi+ instrument with monochromatic Al K α X-ray source. The instrument's binding energy scale was calibrated to give a binding energy at 932.6 eV for Cu 2p $_{3/2}$ line of freshly etched metallic copper. A charge compensation system was used, with the surface of the sample irradiated with a flood of electrons to produce nearly neutral surface charge. The experimental data has been referenced to C 1s adventitious carbon. The spectra were recorded by using an X-ray beam size 650 \times 10 microns, a pass energy of 20 eV and step size 0.1 eV.

2.3. Electrochemical characterization

The electrochemical behavior of the newly developed bio-curved graphene electrode materials in various electrolytes was studied using both a two- and three-electrode test cell design and analysis techniques as described in deliverable D4.1.

For the wood-derived carbon materials, electrode ink was prepared in a beaker using the activated carbon materials, styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR, 50 wt.% water solution), carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) – mass ratio: 88:8:4. Additional water (deionized) was added, resulting in a 1:4.2 solid/solvent total mass ratio. The beaker with the resulting mixture was transferred to an ultrasonic bath and sonicated for 30 min. Afterwards the electrode ink was ball milled for 1 hour at 15 Hz. For black liquor pristine and composite materials, the slurry was mixed with magnetic stirrer for 1 h. The resulting slurry was coated on a graphite foil (T68-270-270-0.025, t-Global Technology) using a doctor-blade at a 150-200 μ m thickness then vacuum dried overnight at 80°C. Finally, electrodes were pressed out as 12 mm diameter disks.

Electrochemical tests were done in a symmetrical coin-cell setup. 316 stainless steel CR2032-type coin-cell casing and Whatman 1821-055 separator was used. The chosen electrolyte was 0.5M K $_2$ HPO $_4$ / 0.5M KH $_2$ PO $_4$ buffer solution. In our previous work¹, we concluded that this electrolyte provided great electrochemical performance and good compatibility with the chosen electrode material.

The measurements were performed with BioLogic VMP3 potentiostat-galvanostat and Maccor 4300 workstation. Selected long-term cycling experiments have been performed with Neware BTS-4000 series tester.

¹ Pourkheirollah, H.; Vitto, R. I. M.; Volperts, A.; Vindt, S. T.; Grinberga, L.; Kučinskis, G.; Keskinen, J.; Mäntysalo, M. Enhancing Specific Capacitance and Energy Density in Printed Supercapacitors: The Role of Activated Wood Carbon and Electrolyte Dynamics. *Carbon Trends* **2025**, *18*, 100436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cartre.2024.100436>.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Bio-curved materials

The morphology of the bio-curved graphene samples was examined using SEM (Figure 1, top images). The samples are in general similar to each other, with main features being irregularly shaped grains, curved structures with micrometer-scale lateral dimensions and sharp edges.

The XRD patterns (Figure 1, bottom left) show broad characteristic (002) diffraction band, confirming graphene-like amorphous structures with reduced crystallite size for all samples, as well as indications of impurities just in the STV samples.

The Raman spectra (Figure 1, bottom right) display the three characteristic bands of graphene-based materials: the D band at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the G band at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and the 2D band at $\sim 2700\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The pronounced D band indicates a high density of defects and edge sites, while the G band confirms the presence of sp^2 -hybridized carbon. The broadened and relatively weak 2D band indicates presence of the few-layer graphene with significant structural disorder.

Figure 1. SEM images (top), XRD patterns (bottom left), and Raman spectra (bottom right) of bio-curved materials

Performance of bio-curved materials are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Performance of bio-curved graphene materials.

Electrode material	BET Surface area [m ² /g]	DFT Surface area [m ² /g]	Electrolyte ID	Specific Capacitance [F/g]	Voltage window [V]
STV231123PMA	--	--	Std. buffer	143	1.2
YP-80F	2220	1352	Std. buffer	107	1.2
YP-50F	1500	1175	Std. buffer	104	1.2
STV240304PMA	--	--	Std. buffer	152	1.2
NHD240327PMA	--	--	Std. buffer	116 (wetting issues)	1.2
NHD240327PMA	--	--	Std. hybrid	187-208 (weight issue)	2
NHD240423PMA #1	--	--	Std. hybrid	200-234	2
NHD240423PMA #2	--	--	Std. hybrid	249-285(thin coating)	2
YP-50F	1500	1175	Std. hybrid	105-125	2
YP-80F	2220	1352	Std. hybrid	109-129	2
STV240508H2	2600	1854	Std. hybrid	188-224	2
STV240508H1	2238	1688	Std. hybrid	258-299 (thin coating)	2
NHD240605PMA	3139	1920	Std. hybrid	191-218	2
NHD240523PMA	3043	1878	Std. hybrid	192-212	~1.9

CC curve of 3 first cycles at +/- 1.8V for NHD240605PMA in Std. Hybrid electrolyte at a 3.94 mA/cm² current density (time on x-axis and voltage on y-axis) is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. CC gravimetric charge-discharge curve of 3 first cycles, axes show voltage (V) vs. time (s).

Figure 3. Cyclic voltammetry curves at 10mV/s (A), galvanostatic charge-discharge curves at 0.1 A/g (B), rate capability (in percentages) from 0.1 to 5 A/g (C) of two NHD240722 samples.

Figure 3 illustrates CV, GCD and rate capability measurements of two symmetrical NHD240722 coin cells using std. buffer as the electrolyte. Average C_s , CE and LC were 209 F/g, 96.4 %, and 0.068 mA/F, respectively.

3.2. Wood-derived materials from different wood species

In total 16 samples were compared by their structural and electrochemical properties. Table 2 shows a summary of sorptometry and electrochemistry data. On average, alder wood carbon (AWC) has the highest specific surface area (S BET), micropore volume, as well as the highest specific capacitance (C_s) values, most notably AWC-3-700 which performed the best with S BET, micropore volume and C_s values – 2844 m²/g, 0.970 cm³/g, 265 F/g, respectively. Across all samples, oak and birch wood carbon (OWC and BWC respectively) had comparable results, while eucalyptus wood carbon (EWC) performed the worst.

Figure 4. Nitrogen sorption at 77K of activated carbons derived from various wood species: (1) - alder, (2) - birch, (3) - oak, (4) - eucalyptus.

Figure 4 illustrates nitrogen sorption isotherms at 77K of activated wood carbons based on various wood species. For alder, oak and birch there are two trends – firstly, increase of NaOH addition ratio increases total nitrogen sorption volume and both 700 and 800 °C activation temperatures. Secondly, there is distinct change of pore size distribution – when at 700 °C isotherms belong to Type I materials, which are characteristic for microporous materials, at 800 °C they are accompanied with H4 type hysteresis, pointing at significant input of slit-like mesopores into total volume of adsorbed N₂.

The situation is different for eucalyptus, since in its case hysteresis appears already at 700 °C and NaOH addition ratio 2, and all further attempts to increase its total volume were not successful. This can be explained by the different cell structure of this precursor compared to the other hardwood species under study.

The observed changes of material properties are supported by pore size distribution charts demonstrated in Figure 5 – these calculations were made using Density Functional Theory. The input of pores with width higher than 2 nm, or mesopores, increases with NaOH addition ratio and, especially, with increase of temperature, reaching the highest values at addition ratio 3 and activation temperature 800 °C.

Figure 5. Pore size distribution of activated carbons derived from various wood species: (1) - alder, (2) - birch, (3) - oak, (4) - eucalyptus.

Numerical values of nitrogen sorption at 77 K tests are presented in Table 2 and further exemplify the observations above: for all the samples under study activation at 700 °C and NaOH addition 2 ratio leads to the highest specific surface areas (BET), with alder wood reaching 2884 m² g⁻¹ and being the leader in this area. Birch and oak samples synthesized in similar conditions demonstrate values of 2401 and 2495 m² g⁻¹, respectively, while eucalyptus reaches only 2168 m² g⁻¹. These samples also have the highest micropore volumes. At the same time the most mesoporous material was obtained at 800 °C and NaOH addition ratio 3, with alder also having the highest volume of 0.840 cm³ g⁻¹.

Table 2. Sorptometry and electrochemistry data of wood-derived materials from different wood species.

Wood species	Sample	S BET, m ² /g	Pore volume, cm ³ /g	Micropore volume, cm ³ /g	Mesopore volume, cm ³ /g	Cs, F/g	CE, %	LC, mA/F
Alder	AWC-2-700	2099	1.030	0.850	0.180	237	93.8	0.094
Alder	AWC-3-700	2844	1.420	0.970	0.450	265	91.9	0.108
Alder	AWC-2-800	2431	1.370	0.840	0.530	218	94.3	0.086
Alder	AWC-3-800	2667	1.650	0.830	0.820	193	93.7	0.097
Birch	BWC-2-700	1973	0.972	0.802	0.170	210	95.2	0.075
Birch	BWC-3-700	2401	1.217	0.888	0.329	247	93.1	0.092
Birch	BWC-2-800	1950	1.090	0.677	0.413	174	95.3	0.081
Birch	BWC-3-800	2315	1.390	0.742	0.648	176	95.0	0.084
Oak	OWC-2-700	2044	1.005	0.807	0.198	202	95.7	0.079
Oak	OWC-3-700	2495	1.249	0.898	0.351	254	90.8	0.115
Oak	OWC-2-800	2065	1.091	0.718	0.373	170	96.6	0.067
Oak	OWC-3-800	2485	1.431	0.795	0.636	205	92.4	0.114
Eucalyptus	EWC-2-700	1590	0.821	0.657	0.164	180	95.8	0.074
Eucalyptus	EWC-3-700	2168	1.098	0.818	0.280	169	91.0	0.140
Eucalyptus	EWC-2-800	1871	1.041	0.691	0.350	164	96.2	0.072
Eucalyptus	EWC-3-800	2053	1.362	0.689	0.673	130	94.8	0.110
Alder, oxidized	AWC-3-700+60min	2486	1.223	0.833	0.39	224	93.2	0.099
Alder, tempered	AWC-3-700_T1000	2760	1.393	0.903	0.49	223	94.2	0.077
YP 50F (Kuraray)	-	1500	0.800	0.61	0.19	110	94.6	0.113
YP 80F (Kuraray)	-	2220	1.150	0.73	0.42	115	97.7	0.051

Treatment of carbons aimed at increasing and decreasing hydrophilicity, e.g. increase and decrease of oxygen containing groups by treatment with H₂O₂ and tempering at 1000 °C also influences porous structure, decreasing specific surface area, which is especially pronounced in the case of oxidizing with hydrogen peroxide. More on these samples in the sub-chapter 3.4 N- and P-Doped Wood Materials and additional processing.

Sorption data on black liquor, hybrid, N and P doped samples will be demonstrated in the corresponding chapter.

Table 3. Elemental analysis of wood-derived materials from different wood species

Wood species	Sample	N, %	C, %	H, %	S, %	O, %
<i>Carbonizates</i>						
Alder	n/a	0.46	86.04	3.84	0.26	9.40
Birch	n/a	0.26	88.69	3.77	0.24	7.04
Oak	n/a	0.34	87.04	3.66	0.20	8.75
Eucalyptus	n/a	0.13	90.99	3.20	0.19	5.50
<i>Activated carbons</i>						
Alder	AWC-2-700	0.71	92.28	2.19	0.23	4.59
Alder	AWC-3-700	0.66	93.27	1.95	0.59	3.53
Alder	AWC-2-800	0.73	92.80	1.38	0.08	5.31
Alder	AWC-3-800	0.66	92.73	1.20	0.09	5.01
Birch	BWC-2-700	0.22	93.15	1.24	0.07	5.32
Birch	BWC-3-700	0.24	93.72	0.91	0.08	5.06
Birch	BWC-2-800	0.26	92.81	1.07	0.09	5.76
Birch	BWC-3-800	0.32	93.42	0.68	0.09	5.48
Oak	OWC-2-700	0.26	93.53	0.72	0.07	5.42
Oak	OWC-3-700	0.30	92.90	0.65	0.05	6.10
Oak	OWC-2-800	0.30	93.42	0.58	0.06	5.65
Oak	OWC-3-800	0.28	94.75	0.58	0.07	4.31
Eucalyptus	EWC-2-700	0.20	93.96	0.61	0.06	5.40
Eucalyptus	EWC-3-700	0.30	94.47	0.71	0.05	4.47
Eucalyptus	EWC-2-800	0.29	93.72	0.73	0.05	5.21
Eucalyptus	EWC-3-800	0.27	94.25	0.81	0.05	4.62
Alder, oxidized	AWC-3-700+60min	0.35	80.43	1.10	0.12	18.00
Alder, tempered	AWC-3-700_T1000	0.44	96.77	0.65	0.12	2.01
<i>Black liquor and hybrid samples</i>						
Black liquor	ABL-2-700	0.56	72.80	1.18	14.67	10.79
Black liquor	ABL-3-700	0.12	1.61	1.94	47.96	48.37
Black liquor	ABL-2-800	0.49	70.07	2.32	15.94	11.18
Black liquor	ABL-3-800	0.10	2.49	2.17	31.30	63.94
Hybrid	AWC-ABL-1/1-2-700	0.66	91.35	0.37	0.71	6.91
Hybrid	AWC-ABL-1/1-3-700	0.92	90.44	0.33	0.50	7.81
Hybrid	AWC-ABL-1/2-1-700	0.55	91.47	1.69	0.22	6.06
Hybrid	AWC-ABL-1/2-2-700	0.73	91.42	0.40	2.26	5.19
Hybrid	AWC-ABL-1/1-2-800	0.50	89.09	0.74	0.16	9.50
Hybrid	AWC-ABL-1/1-3-800	0.63	94.23	0.47	0.28	4.40
Hybrid	AWC-ABL-1/2-1-800	0.60	94.26	0.56	0.16	4.42
Hybrid	AWC-ABL-1/2-2-800	0.76	93.44	0.46	1.72	3.62

The elemental composition of wood species carbonizates and activated carbons on their base is demonstrated in

Wood species	Sample	S BET, m ² /g	Pore volume, cm ³ /g	Micropore volume, cm ³ /g	Mesopore volume, cm ³ /g	Cs, F/g	CE, %	LC, mA/F
Alder	AWC-2-700	2099	1.030	0.850	0.180	237	93.8	0.094
Alder	AWC-3-700	2844	1.420	0.970	0.450	265	91.9	0.108
Alder	AWC-2-800	2431	1.370	0.840	0.530	218	94.3	0.086
Alder	AWC-3-800	2667	1.650	0.830	0.820	193	93.7	0.097
Birch	BWC-2-700	1973	0.972	0.802	0.170	210	95.2	0.075
Birch	BWC-3-700	2401	1.217	0.888	0.329	247	93.1	0.092
Birch	BWC-2-800	1950	1.090	0.677	0.413	174	95.3	0.081
Birch	BWC-3-800	2315	1.390	0.742	0.648	176	95.0	0.084
Oak	OWC-2-700	2044	1.005	0.807	0.198	202	95.7	0.079
Oak	OWC-3-700	2495	1.249	0.898	0.351	254	90.8	0.115
Oak	OWC-2-800	2065	1.091	0.718	0.373	170	96.6	0.067
Oak	OWC-3-800	2485	1.431	0.795	0.636	205	92.4	0.114
Eucalyptus	EWC-2-700	1590	0.821	0.657	0.164	180	95.8	0.074
Eucalyptus	EWC-3-700	2168	1.098	0.818	0.280	169	91.0	0.140
Eucalyptus	EWC-2-800	1871	1.041	0.691	0.350	164	96.2	0.072
Eucalyptus	EWC-3-800	2053	1.362	0.689	0.673	130	94.8	0.110
Alder, oxidized	AWC-3-700+60min	2486	1.223	0.833	0.39	224	93.2	0.099
Alder, tempered	AWC-3-700_T1000	2760	1.393	0.903	0.49	223	94.2	0.077
YP 50F (Kuraray)	-	1500	0.800	0.61	0.19	110	94.6	0.113
YP 80F (Kuraray)	-	2220	1.150	0.73	0.42	115	97.7	0.051

Treatment of carbons aimed at increasing and decreasing hydrophilicity, e.g. increase and decrease of oxygen containing groups by treatment with H₂O₂ and tempering at 1000 °C also influences porous structure, decreasing specific surface area, which is especially pronounced in the case of oxidizing with hydrogen peroxide. More on these samples in the sub-chapter 3.4 N- and P-Doped Wood Materials and additional processing.

Sorption data on black liquor, hybrid, N and P doped samples will be demonstrated in the corresponding chapter.

Table 3 shows that content of oxygen in alder carbonizate is the highest, which makes it more responsive to NaOH activation. This is supported by the oxygen content in oak, birch and eucalyptus – each of these species is subsequently less susceptible to activation and showing lower specific areas.

Oxygen content in activated carbons shows two tendencies – firstly, the higher NaOH addition rate is, the higher oxygen content is in the resulting material, and, secondly, higher activation temperature leads to reduction in the content of oxygen functional groups.

In the case of black liquor, addition of NaOH in ratio of 3 almost completely gasifies the material, leading to very low content of carbon and proportionally very high sulfur content.

SEM, XRD and Raman spectroscopy were used to analyze surface and structure of samples.

The particle structure of the various samples is very similar across all wood species based on SEM images. As an example, Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9 depict SEM images of OWC samples. The analysis showed a broad distribution of particle sizes, ranging from just a few nanometers – often clustered around larger particles – to several tens of micrometers. In some instances, it is possible to see small sheet-like shapes on the particles which could indicate the presence of graphene structures.

Figure 6. SEM: OWC-2-700

Figure 7. SEM: OWC-2-800

Figure 8. SEM: OWC-3-700

Figure 9. SEM: OWC-3-800

To analyze correlation between electrochemical performance and the structure of the samples XRD analysis and Raman spectroscopy were used.

According to literature, for XRD patterns a peak around 26.4° can be attributed to the (002) plane of the ordered graphitized structure and a broad peak around 43.3° to the diffraction of (100/101) planes in the disordered amorphous structure. At higher temperatures due to graphene reduction, the shift of the peak around 26.4° to lower 2θ values is observed.² A broad peak around 18° – 40° could be related to inhomogeneous rGO layers³ or amorphous carbon⁴. Peaks at around 42.41° , 44.36° and 50.38° may be

² Pourkheirollah, H.; Vitto, R. I. M.; Volperts, A.; Vindt, S. T.; Grinberga, L.; Kučinskis, G.; Keskinen, J.; Mäntysalo, M. Enhancing Specific Capacitance and Energy Density in Printed Supercapacitors: The Role of Activated Wood Carbon and Electrolyte Dynamics. *Carbon Trends* **2025**, *18*, 100436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cartre.2024.100436>.

³ Taratayko, A.; Kolobova, E.; Mamontov, G. Graphene Oxide Decorated with Ag and CeO₂ Nanoparticles as a Catalyst for Room-Temperature 4-Nitrophenol Reduction. *Catalysts*, **2022**, *12*, 1393. <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal12111393>

⁴ Li, D.; Tian, F.; Chu, B.; Duan, D.; Sha, X.; Lv, Y.; Zhang, H.; Lu, N.; Liu B.; Cui T. *Ab initio* structure determination of n-diamond. *Sci Rep* **2015**, *5*, 13447. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep13447>

attributed to the hexagonal phases of the (100), (101) and (102) planes; 43.45° - to the rhombohedral phases of the (100) plane.⁵

Figure 10. XRD patterns for AWC (top left), BWC (top right), OWC (bottom left) and EWC (bottom right) samples.

XRD patterns (Figure 10) show that samples heated to 700°C generally are disordered, and no correlation with activator amount is observed. When heated to 800°C, all the samples have a distinct peak assigned to the ordered graphitized structure (26.4°); for some of the samples it is asymmetric, with broader left (smaller 2θ values) wing due to reduction processes. Birch- and oak-based samples show multiple peaks around 42° - 45°, indicating hexagonal and rhombohedral phases. Also, increased activator amount results in stronger peaks for these two materials. Comparing these patterns with electrochemical measurements, we conclude that for better performance material should have both ordered and disordered structures, and it is more common for the samples heated till 700°.

Raman spectra of the activated bio-chars (Figure 11) show the characteristic D (~1350 cm⁻¹), G (~1580 cm⁻¹), and 2D (~2700 cm⁻¹) bands of disordered graphitic carbon. The pronounced D band in most samples indicates a high density of defects and exposed edge sites introduced by a higher rate of activation. Increasing the carbonization temperature generally narrows the G band and enhances the 2D feature, consistent with partial graphitization and improved in-plane order. Among the species, alder-

⁵ Kim, Y.S.; Hanif, M.A.; Song, H.; Kim, S.; Cho, Y.; Ryu, S.-K.; Kim, H.G. Wood-Derived Graphite: A Sustainable and Cost-Effective Material for the Wide Range of Industrial Applications. *Crystals* **2024**, *14*, 309.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst14040309>

derived carbons exhibit a favorable balance of order and defects, with moderate D and G band ratios at higher temperatures and moderate activation levels, suggesting partially ordered carbon with sufficient edge sites for electrochemical activity. Birch shows a more pronounced D band, indicative of highly disordered carbon, while oak and eucalyptus exhibit variable D-band intensity. The appearance of the 2D band, mostly at 800°C, indicates the formation of graphene-like domains or stacked graphitic layers. This graphitization can reduce accessible surface area for ions, lowering capacitance.

Figure 11. Raman spectra for AWC (top left), BWC (top right), OWC (bottom left) and EWC (bottom right) samples.

Overall, these Raman trends correlate with the electrochemical performance data. Alder samples display the highest capacitance and surface area, consistent with a structure that balances graphitic ordering for conductivity and sufficient defects for charge storage.

Specific pore area, pore size distribution and functional group content influence supercapacitor properties, which is demonstrated below.

To better understand how the carbon surface structure affects the electrochemical performance of the electrodes, a better visualization of these properties can be seen in Figure 12 which presents a scatter plot showing the correlation between C_s and S BET, and Figure 13 that depicts the relation between C_s and micropore volume. In both cases there seems to be a positive trend, although the correlation between capacitance and S BET is not as clear as initially expected. Rather, the micropore volume seems to have a larger impact on the resulting capacitance.

Figure 12. Scatter plot: average specific capacitance (C_s) versus specific surface area (S_{BET}).

Looking at each wood species separately, Figure 13 illustrates that BWC and OWC samples have a strong linear correlation between C_s and micropore volume, while AWC has more of a logarithmic trend. This could imply that there are possible diminishing returns on supercapacitor performance at high micropore volumes. EWC samples show poor correlation in both metrics, indicating other limiting factors for this sample group (e.g., pore accessibility, conductivity).

Figure 13. Scatter plot: average specific capacitance (Cs) versus micropore volume.

Figure 14 depicts coulombic efficiency (CE) and leakage current (LC) values. Across all samples, higher activation temperature (800 °C) tends to improve CE and reduce LC, though not significantly. A more significant trend can be seen comparing activator amount (3 vs 2). Higher activator amount seems to be associated with lower CE and higher LC. This may indicate over-activation, leading to structural instability. Despite this, 3-700 sample series showed the highest Cs values in almost all instances, with EWC being an outlier. This suggests that some high-capacitance samples may suffer from higher leakage, reducing their efficiency and power delivery.

Figure 14. Average coulombic efficiency (A) and leakage current (B) data of wood-derived carbon material supercapacitors of various wood species.

It should be noted that higher S BET and micropore volume seem to be associated with lower CE and LC. As an example, Figure 15 illustrates a negative correlation between CE and micropore volume. This suggests that excessive porosity may lead to charge leakage, possibly due to poor ion confinement or increased side reactions.

Figure 15. Scatter plot: average coulombic efficiency vs micropore volume.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD), and rate capability results for all samples are summarized in Figure 16, Figure 17, Figure 18, and Figure 19. CV curves across all samples exhibit relatively similar quasi-rectangular shapes, with a noticeable steepening of the curve between approximately 0.8 and 1 V in the anodic sweep. This feature may indicate the presence of irreversible Faradaic reactions. Samples from series 3-700 and 3-800 across all wood species tend to show slightly steeper curves compared to 2-700 and 2-800. Their lower oxidation stability could be attributed to a potentially higher oxygen concentration on the surface of these carbon samples, likely resulting from the increased amount of activator used during synthesis.

To evaluate rate capability, samples were cycled at various current densities (0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, and 5.0 A/g). For alder, birch, and oak, the best-performing samples were from the 3-800 series, retaining 76–83% of their capacitance when increasing the current density from 0.1 to 5 A/g. Although there is notable variation in performance across wood species, series 2-700 and 2-800 generally exhibited the poorest capacitance retention (23–72% and 16–67%, respectively). Interestingly, for eucalyptus, the highest retention was observed in the 2-700 sample (73%), making it a notable outlier compared to its performance in other wood species.

Figure 16. Cyclic voltammetry curves at 10mV/s (A), galvanostatic charge-discharge curves at 0.1 A/g (B), rate capability (in percentages) from 0.1 to 5 A/g (C) of AWC samples.

Figure 17. Cyclic voltammetry curves at 10mV/s (A), galvanostatic charge-discharge curves at 0.1 A/g (B), rate capability (in percentages) from 0.1 to 5 A/g (C) of BWC samples.

Figure 18. Cyclic voltammetry curves at 10mV/s (A), galvanostatic charge-discharge curves at 0.1 A/g (B), rate capability (in percentages) from 0.1 to 5 A/g (C) of OWC samples.

Figure 19. Cyclic voltammetry curves at 10mV/s (A), galvanostatic charge-discharge curves at 0.1 A/g (B), rate capability (in percentages) from 0.1 to 5 A/g (C) of EWC samples.

Among the 16 wood-derived carbon samples studied, alder (AWC) consistently outperformed others in surface area, micropore volume, and specific capacitance, with AWC-3-700 being the top performer. Birch (BWC) and oak (OWC) showed similar results, while eucalyptus (EWC) lagged behind. Capacitance correlated more strongly with micropore volume than surface area, with diminishing returns observed at high porosity levels. Higher activation temperatures slightly improved efficiency, but excessive activator amounts led to increased leakage and reduced stability. Despite this, 3-series samples generally had better rate capability, especially in AWC, BWC, and OWC, while EWC remained an outlier with inconsistent performance.

3.3. Wood- and black liquor-derived composite materials

The electrochemical and structural properties of activated wood carbon (AWC) activated black liquor carbon (ABL), and their composite materials (AWC-ABL) were evaluated to further explore the effect of precursor combinations, activation conditions, and synthesis parameters on the performance of carbon-based electrodes. The use of Activated Black Liquor (ABL) as a carbon precursor is motivated by its origin as a waste stream from the kraft pulping process, where lignin, hemicellulose, and inorganic chemicals are removed from wood to produce paper pulp. Developing value-added applications for ABL – such as in electrode materials – therefore presents a dual advantage: valorizing a waste product and reducing its ecological impact.

As described in previous chapter, the sample naming convention provides detailed information about synthesis parameters:

- The number following the precursor code (e.g., 2 or 3 in AWC-2-700) denotes the activator amount used during chemical activation.
- The final digits (700 or 800) indicate the activation temperature in °C.
- For composite samples (AWC-ABL), additional ratios such as 1/1 or 1/2 specify the mass ratio of AWC to ABL precursors used prior to activation.

For pristine AWC samples, the reader is referred back to the previous chapters and Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 4. Sorptometry and electrochemistry data of wood-derived materials from different wood species. Data for AWC series can be seen previously.

Sample	$S_{BET}, m^2 g^{-1}$	$V, cm^3 g^{-1}$	$V_{micro}, cm^3 g^{-1}$	$C_{sp}, F g^{-1}$	Energy density, $Wh kg^{-1}$	LC, μA	$\mu_t, \%$
ABL-2-700	2272	1.93	0.73	-	-	-	-
ABL-3-700	196	0.17	0.07	4.81	0.7	248.0	81.7
ABL-2-800	2104	2.33	0.60	61	8.5	6.9	91.5
ABL-3-800	2	0.02	-	-	-	-	-
AWC-ABL-1/1-2-700	2521	1.24	0.93	237	33.7	17.5	93.9
AWC-ABL-1/1-3-700	3120	1.78	0.99	250	34.4	16.7	93.6
AWC-ABL-1/2-1-700	1557	0.83	0.65	218	30.2	25.3	96.2
AWC-ABL-1/2-2-700	2788	1.45	0.95	229	31.4	19.2	93.8
AWC-ABL-1/1-2-800	2139	1.29	0.68	175	24.0	14.7	95.5
AWC-ABL-1/1-3-800	2969	2.21	0.95	197	27.9	11.7	94.4
AWC-ABL-1/2-1-800	1481	0.80	0.58	167	23.3	19.2	95.3
AWC-ABL-1/2-2-800	2833	1.71	0.90	232	32.2	11.0	95.1

Structural characterization

The structural parameters of the composite materials are summarized in Table 2. Across all samples, the AWC samples exhibited higher specific surface area (S_{BET}) values, with AWC-3-700 reaching $2844 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, surpassing all other individual materials. ABL materials, on the other hand, displayed lower surface areas and pore volumes, with the ABL-3-700 and ABL-3-800 samples showing particularly low structural development.

Composite samples combining AWC and ABL precursors generally showed intermediate to high S_{BET} values depending on the mixing ratio. Notably, AWC-ABL-1/1-3-700 achieved the highest surface area of $3120 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, suggesting that optimized precursor combinations can lead to synergistic effects in porosity development. Increasing the activation temperature from $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ led to a reduction in surface area and micropore volume in several samples, indicating partial pore collapse or structural coarsening at higher temperatures.

Figure 20. XRD patterns and Ramans spectra for the ABL, AWC and ABL composite samples.

XRD analysis (Figure 20, left) of the activated wood carbon and activated black liquor carbon composites shows a broad (002) reflection at $\sim 22\text{--}26^\circ$, characteristic of amorphous carbon, with a weak (100) shoulder near $\sim 43\text{--}45^\circ$ indicating limited in-plane graphitic ordering. Sharp peaks in some samples could arise from residual inorganic phases, more pronounced in AWC-ABL-1/1-3-700, reflecting a possible mineral carryover from the precursor.

Raman spectra (Figure 20, right) of the ABL, and AWC and ABL composites exhibit the characteristic D ($\sim 1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and G ($\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) bands typical of disordered graphitic carbon. The presence of an intense D band together with a broadened G band confirms that all are amorphous and defect-rich samples, while observed differences in the relative band intensities among samples show variations in defect density and structural ordering. At higher carbonization temperatures, a weak 2D band ($\sim 2700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) shows up, indicating partial graphitization and the development of graphene-like domains.

Electrochemical performance

Across all materials, charge–discharge profiles are observed, characteristic of predominantly double-layer capacitance behavior (Figure 21). However, samples exhibiting higher specific capacitance (C_{sp}) values display discharge curves that deviate slightly from perfect linearity, particularly at higher voltages.

Figure 21. The GCD curves for AWC-only samples, ABL-only samples and composite AWC-ABL samples, respectively.

Across all materials, the CV profiles (Figure 22) exhibit quasi-rectangular shapes characteristic of double-layer capacitive behavior with minimal Faradaic contributions. However, notable differences arise between precursor types and activation parameters:

AWC samples show the largest enclosed areas, reflecting their high specific capacitance values C_{sp} . Some distortion of the ideal rectangular shape at voltages above 0.8 V is observed for samples with the highest C_{sp} , suggesting possible pseudocapacitive contributions or increased surface functionalities introduced by more aggressive activation (e.g., higher activator ratios).

ABL samples display much narrower CV profiles with significantly lower current densities, consistent with their low surface area, low micropore volume, and hence low capacitance.

AWC-ABL composites exhibit intermediate to high current densities depending on the precursor ratio and activation temperature. Several formulations achieve nearly rectangular CV curves

with large, enclosed areas, indicating that precursor mixing can yield favorable combinations of porosity and conductivity. Nevertheless, the composite curves remain less ideal than those of the best-performing AWC samples, suggesting that the incorporation of ABL introduces structural or conductivity limitations compared to pure AWC materials.

Figure 22. The cyclic voltammetry curves for AWC-only, ABL-only, and AWC-ABL composite samples measured at 10 mV s^{-1} .

Overall, the CV results corroborate the GCD findings: higher capacitance samples tend to deviate slightly from ideal capacitive behavior, especially at higher potentials, possibly due to surface redox reactions or ion transport effects within highly porous structures.

The electrochemical properties of the materials were evaluated in terms of specific capacitance (C_{sp}), coulombic efficiency (μt), and leakage current (LC), as summarized in Table 4. C_{sp} value of 265 F g^{-1} , consistent with its superior SBET and micropore volume. By contrast, ABL-only materials demonstrated substantially lower capacitance, with ABL-3-700 delivering only 4.8 F g^{-1} , reflecting their limited structural development.

Composite samples exhibited improved electrochemical performance compared to ABL alone, with several formulations achieving capacitance values comparable to or exceeding those of pure AWC materials. Specifically, AWC-ABL-1/1-3-700 and AWC-ABL-1/1-2-700 delivered C_{sp} values of 250.2 F g^{-1} and 237.0 F g^{-1} , respectively, highlighting the potential of mixed precursors for tuning both porosity and electrochemical properties.

Correlation between structure and performance

Micropore volume ($V_{\text{micropores}}$) is directly proportional to specific capacitance (C_{sp}) across all sample types, indicating the critical role of microporous structures in enhancing double-layer charge storage (Figure 23).

Figure 23. The relationship between the micropore volume and specific capacitance for AWC, ABL, and AWC-ABL samples

AWC samples consistently exhibit the highest C_{sp} values at comparable micropore volumes, while ABL materials remain limited by both low porosity and low capacitance. Composite AWC-ABL samples follow the general positive trend but with slightly greater data spread, reflecting the effect of precursor mixing on pore size distribution and electrochemical behavior.

Figure 24. The relationship between the total pore volume (left), or the specific surface area (right) and specific capacitance for AWC, ABL, and AWC-ABL samples

At micropore volumes above approximately $0.8 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$, the increase in capacitance begins to plateau, suggesting diminishing returns at high porosities where ion transport limitations or pore accessibility constraints may reduce effective capacitance utilization.

Like the micropore volume trend, higher pore volumes generally correspond to increased capacitance, with AWC and selected AWC-ABL samples achieving the highest C_{sp} values (Figure 24, left). However, the correlation appears weaker for total pore volume compared to micropore volume, particularly at larger pore sizes. Similar tendencies are observed for the S_{bet} too (Figure 24, right). This suggests that while mesopores contribute to ion transport and rate performance, the microporous fraction dominates double-layer capacitance formation. Composite samples with balanced micro- and mesoporous structures, such as AWC-ABL-1/1-3-700 (that is compared to ABL-2-800 in Figure 25), show optimal performance, combining relatively high capacitance with efficient ion accessibility.

Figure 25. SEM images of ABL-2-800 (top) and AWC-ABL-1/1-3-700 (bottom) composite at different magnifications

3.4. N- and P-Doped Wood Materials and additional processing

Several post-processing methods were tested on selected wood carbon samples to see how they would affect the structural and electrochemical properties of these materials.

XRD patterns of the AWC and doped samples exhibit a broad (002) reflection around 22–26°, characteristic of amorphous carbon with limited graphitic ordering, and a weak (100) peak near 43–45°, reflecting short-range in-plane order. The AWC, AWC-H₂O₂ and AWC-T_1000 samples show similar amorphous features, where the sharp peaks indicate some level of graphitization, while the nitrogen doped sample has no sharp peaks. Phosphorous doped samples have more intense amorphous bands, but overall, the patterns confirm that the carbons remain largely disordered, with slight structural modifications introduced by oxidative and temperature treatments rather than extensive graphitic stacking. (Figure 26, left).

Raman spectra of alder wood activated carbons show the typical D (~1350 cm⁻¹) and G (~1580 cm⁻¹) bands, confirming a mix of disordered and graphitic domains. The pristine AWC-3-700, P doped AWC-P-2-700, and the oxidized AWC-3-700-H₂O₂ display high and broad D band, indicating significant structural disorder.

In contrast, thermal treatment at 1000 °C (AWC-3-700-T1000) and nitrogen modification (AWC-3-700-N) reduces the D band, indicating partial ordering and improved graphitization. The broad, weak 2D features further confirm the amorphous nature of the materials. (Figure 26, right)

Figure 26. XRD patterns and Raman spectra of doped samples, adjusted axis for better resolution

Electrochemical measurements are depicted in Figure 27. All samples exhibit quasi-rectangular CV curves, with slight differences between some samples. The N-doped samples exhibited the most pronounced rounding at the beginning of both the anodic and cathodic sweeps, suggesting higher internal resistance within the cell. In contrast, the curve steepening between 0.8 and 1 V in the anodic sweep was less evident for the P-doped sample, although it reached only half the maximum current observed in the other samples. GCD analysis shows that AWC-3-700-H₂O₂ has a non-linear discharge curve which could be caused by the increased amount of oxygen in the carbon material. The presence of oxygen-containing functional groups could introduce pseudocapacitive behavior.

Figure 27. Cyclic voltammetry curves at 10mV/s (A), and galvanostatic charge-discharge curves at 0.1 A/g (B).

Table 5 depicts a summary of the main parameters for pristine and modified AWC-3-700 samples. Modifying the carbon material reduced the Cs values by a significant amount, especially in the case of P-doping. On the other hand, CE and LC improved, most notably for N- and P-doped samples, indicating that doping might increase conductivity or reduce unwanted side-reactions by stabilizing the surface structure. There does not seem to be clear correlation between S BET and the electrochemical performance in this case, suggesting that other factors such as surface chemistry may play a more dominant role.

Table 5. Comparative overview of S BET and electrochemical parameters of pristine AWC-3-700 and modified variations.

Sample	S BET, m ² /g	Cs, F/g	CE, %	LC, mA/F
AWC-3-700	2844	265	91.9	0.108
AWC-3-700-H ₂ O ₂	2486	224	93.2	0.099
AWC-3-700-T1000	2760	223	94.2	0.077
AWC-3-700-N	2634	201	96.5	0.062
AWC-3-700-P	1338	95	97.3	0.062

4. Conclusions

The structural and electrochemical evaluation of bio-curved, wood-derived, black liquor, composite, and doped carbons provides the following key findings:

- **Bio-curved carbons** derived from pistachio shells achieved surface areas above $3000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and baseline capacitance $>200 \text{ F g}^{-1}$.
- **Wood-derived carbons** showed strong dependence on precursor species. Alder (AWC) consistently outperformed birch (BWC), oak (OWC), and eucalyptus (EWC). The best-performing sample, AWC-3-700, reached $2844 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ surface area, $0.97 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ micropore volume, and 265 F g^{-1} capacitance.
- Black liquor-derived carbons (ABL) alone exhibited poor performance ($<10 \text{ F g}^{-1}$), but may be a promising additive, as AWC–ABL composites achieved surface areas up to $3120 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and capacitances comparable to AWC ($>230 \text{ F g}^{-1}$).
- Capacitance correlated more strongly with micropore volume than with total surface area, with diminishing returns observed at very high porosity while activation temperature ($800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ vs $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) generally increased coulombic efficiency and reduced leakage current but could lower capacitance due to partial pore collapse.
- Post-processing and doping modified material behavior:
 - Oxidation with H_2O_2 reduced surface area and increased pseudocapacitive contributions.
 - Tempering at $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ improved coulombic efficiency and reduced leakage while reducing capacitance
 - Nitrogen and phosphorus doping reduced capacitance (to $\sim 200 \text{ F g}^{-1}$ and $\sim 95 \text{ F g}^{-1}$, respectively) but enhanced efficiency ($>96\%$).

AWC-3-700 and AWC samples in general (made from alder wood) are identified as the most promising electrode materials, combining high capacitance with favorable structural properties. For the upscaling, and roll-to-roll electrode development, which falls under Task 2.1b, a sub-task of T2.1, $\sim 600\text{g}$ grams of AWC-3-700 were already preliminarily produced in one batch, of which 500 g were delivered to CIDETEC on the 14th April of 2025. Subsequent upscaling efforts are continued during the next year in T1.4.

5. Disclaimer

This document reflects only the views of its authors. The European Union and the granting authority are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The results and conclusions presented herein are based on experiments and analyses carried out under specific laboratory conditions, and while every effort has been made to ensure accuracy, no warranty is given regarding their completeness or applicability in other contexts. The consortium members of the ARMS project shall not be held liable for any damages or losses resulting from the use of this document or the information contained within.

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